

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE EXPRESSION OF NATIONAL REALIAS IN TRANSLATIONS OF ZULFIYA'S POETRY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7940879>

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Abstract.

Article describes the realia of translation in lyric poetry, some factual and conceptual problems and their solutions, description of realia of words of Uzbek poetess Zulfiya's works.

Keywords.

realia, factual, conceptual, complexity of the translation, originality.

"*Realia*" has not been introduced into linguistics for a long time, therefore its main semantic-functional features are considered a very little-studied area from a scientific and theoretical point of view. Florin first used the term in translation studies⁷³. In particular, in the study by Zakhidjon Sadykov "Translation of ancient Turkic realities" the problem of translation of realities is considered. For example, the translation of the Uzbek word "chopon" into Russian as "халат" is rightly criticized in some sources, and on the basis of research it is proved that this word is borrowed into Russian in the same way as in the Uzbek language, on the basis of semantic adaptation. K. Jalilov points to the difference between the cultures of the original language and the target language as one of the main difficulties that arise in the process of translation, and the problem of providing an adequate alternative to real words that are an expression of this difference in the language, that is, words and phrases expressing concepts that are characteristic for a particular culture.⁷⁴

The problem of finding an alternative to realism in the language of translation was dealt with by such Western and Russian scholars as Nedergaard-Larsen, Aikhela, Leppihalme, Pedersen, Ramer, Sintas, L. S. Barkhudarov, S. Vlahov, V. Komissarov.

⁷³ Florin, Cider. Realities in translation . In: Zlateva, Palma (ed. and trans.), Translation as social action. Russian and Bulgarian views. London and New York: Routledge, 1993/122–128.

⁷⁴ Uzbek literature: influence and typology. in the book Jalilov K. Problems of expressing real words of the Uzbek language in English. 341 r

Since reality is a unique thing-phenomenon, a concept associated with the life, culture, history of a certain people, it is natural that many realities can be seen in the lyrics of the nationalist and philanthropic poetess Zulfiya. In her translations, translator B. Kholbekova used a unique method of searching for alternative words.

There are a number of principles of translation studies when describing the national features of realism in translation, and we must pay attention to all scientific aspects of translation in order to identify their main content in the national language. For example, one word "translation" has many meanings, it has two meanings of interest from the point of view of translation studies ⁷⁵.

Firstly, translation is a cognitive activity that determines the process of transferring content expressed in one language using other language means.

The second represents the result of this process, that is, an oral or written text. Despite the difference in these meanings, they have a dialectical commonality with each other. One of the founders of Russian translation studies A.V. Fedorov, translation means the ability to correctly and fully express what is expressed by means of one language, by means of another language. From the point of view of researchers, they are determined by belonging to a particular linguistic school; - the process of describing diots described in the original language using the target language: - reconstruction of the structure of the work in speech, as a result of which the context of the utterance changes, i.e. one language is replaced by another.

Words denoting ideas about life characteristic of a particular people and nation are called realities. According to the dictionary definition, reality is "material and cultural things". In linguistics and translation studies, words and expressions denoting these things, as well as set expressions containing such words, are called "realities". The problems associated with the study of linguistic realities, their transmission in translation, lexicographic definition and linguodidactic presentation are covered in the works of linguists and cultural scientists. The monograph of the Bulgarian translators S. Vlahov and S. Florin "Untranslatable Aspects in Translation" ("Untranslatable in Translation") is one of the important works devoted to the study of reality. When translating into the native language, it is necessary to first determine the information and methodological tasks that are performed in certain contexts, and then select words in the target language that are

⁷⁵ Basic Literary Theory. Moscow: 1971. Enlightenment, 464 p.

suitable for them in all respects, at the same time, at the level of norms and culture of this language ⁷⁶.

Let's try to study the poetess Zulfiya on the basis of the above classifications. In Zulfiya's poems we can find many geographical toponyms. "Hot Africa, Oinakul, Kokchatov, singing Asia, free Port Said, beautiful Bulgaria, Chardzhuy, Kungyrot, a satellite of the Pamirs, beautiful Moscow, beautiful Egypt, Cairo, Afrosyab, Azerbaijan, Baghdad, Ceylon, India, Shakhimardan, Drove, Temirtov steel, Vurgun country, Kazakh Yeshik lake, Balkhash lake, Choli Malik, White Water, Blue Water, Khamzaabad, Nepal, Vietnam, China, etc. In the translation of translator V. Kholbekova, we are faced with the following situation.

Кўшиқ солиб келган ҳар шоир дилга.

Нил қудратин жўшиб куйлар бир шоир.

Ўзгаси **Ганг** мисол қилар замзама.

Фақат манго нусха ажойиб чодир⁷⁷

In translation:

Another bard shows his love

For **the Ganges** tonight.

For us, the shelter is a wonderful tent,

This is the shape of the mango grand.⁷⁸

In this translation, the name of the river Ganges is translated directly, but the word "zamzama" is omitted from the translation. "Mango-copy of the great tent" turns into "mango-grand form", and the Uzbek reality "tent" turns into "mango-grand". From this we can conclude that geographical realities are easily translated in the process of translation, but, on the other hand, it becomes clear that the nationality of toponyms creates difficulties for the translator.

As another example, let's look at a passage about place names.

Салқин сахарларда, бодом гулида, Бинафша лабида, ерларда
баҳор. Қушларнинг парвози, елларнинг нози, **Бахмал водийларда**, қирларда
баҳор.⁷⁹

Translation :

Good sunrises? In almond blossoms

Spring has come, beautiful spring.

⁷⁶Vlakhov S., Florin S. Untranslatable in translation. M-1980.134 gr. Eastern poetics. Specification of the divine image. M.: 1983. S. 123-139. ; Volkov I.F. Theoretical Literature. M.: 2015. S. 98.; Vinogradov V.S. Language and translation. M-2001.

⁷⁷ Xotira siniqlari: she'rlar. Zulfiya. - Toshkent: Adabiyot uchqunlari, 2018 91 bet

⁷⁸ Zulfiya. I was in love. Poetry. Translation by V. Kholbekova. Tashkent. "Academic Edition" p. 14

⁷⁹ Xotira siniqlari: she'rlar. Zulfiya. - Toshkent: Adabiyot uchqunlari, 2018 61 bet

In **velvet valleys** , in lilac lips,
Spring smiled, beautiful spring⁸⁰

In the passage, the phrase "Салқин саҳарларда " is adequately translated as " in almond blossoms". Factuality has retained its place. However, even if the phrase "Баҳмал водийларда " is literally translated as the name of a geographical place, the phrase "velvet valley" in addition to the name of the place means melancholy and longing. It seems to us that the meaning of the poem in English is lost.

One can cite many examples of the work of the poetess Zulfiya, rich in ethnographic realities. "cotton threshing floor, pen, wide porch, bakhshi, caravan, people, revenge, painting, pipe, dumbira, kamzul, snipe, peasant, cotton, mirab, artist, mausoleum, epic, shalola, mushoira, poetic chaman, supa, mirishkor, kasib, Indian sandals, Punjabi kavshi, Mongolian boots, Punjabi nightingale, hijran, itkit zima, kiigin yip" and others.

Қай дил чамани бой, жозиб нафаси,
Кимнинг фикри ўткир, теран, бокира?
Бу гурунг – шоирлар мусобақаси –
Шарқ шеърий чамани, бу мушоира!⁸¹

Translation:

Whose soul is rich, who is nicer?
All deep thoughts are here.
Poets sing in lively conversation,
Oriental flower garden is mushoira .⁸²

In Begoim Kholbekova's translation into English, the sentence "mushoira" was left in this passage as it is, and an attempt was made to convey it to the reader in English. The variant "dil chamani" "the soul is rich" is used.

If we talk about the translation of the poet's poem "Farzand", then the author expressed the will of the real Uzbek childish people. He skillfully sang oriental love for a child.

Nega sevmay, erkalab o'pmay,
Nechun demay uni hayotim?
Nega demay ko'zinning nuri,
So'zlaganda qandim, novvotim?

Translation:

Why not loving, not caressing, not kissing,

⁸⁰ Zulfiya. I was in love. Poetry. Translation by B. Kholbekova . Tashkent. "Academic Edition" p. 16

⁸¹ Зулфия. Ўйлар садоси. Тошкент. 1995 йил. 78-бет

⁸² Zulfiya. I was in love. Poetry. Translation Kholbekova B. Tashkent. "Academic Edition" p.16

Why don't I tell him my life?

Why don't I tell him by the light of the eye?

Why won't I say, my sweet, honey?⁸³

The use of the word "novvotim" by the poet in relation to the child of S. Vlahov can be attributed to the category of ethnographic realities indicated above. In translation, the word " novvotim " is translated as " honey ". But in English there is no suitable equivalent for the word "novot". We believe that the fact that each nation has its own mentality, customs and way of life makes it difficult to translate the poem into English. We have every reason to call the word " novvotim" a national reality. In the process of translation, Kholbekova B. used an analogue of the word "novvotim" and does not have a complete understanding of the word "novvotim".

In the current conditions of globalization, especially within the framework of the influence of the English language on the Uzbek language, the issue of reality is very complex, including its relevance. In our opinion, the leading theoretician Gaibulla Salomov admitted in his notes that in the discussion about translation studies or the theory of translation it is necessary to study the question of reality.

When translating realities into a second language, it is necessary to first determine their information and methodological tasks in specific contexts, and then select words in the target language that are suitable for them in all respects, and at the same time - at the level of norms and culture of this language.

When translating Zulfiya's works into English, the original language variants of realities and exotic lexical units against the background of phonetic, morphological and orthographic adaptation or in the author's version do not reduce the value of the translation.

So, Zulfiya's poetry, its main motives, variety of style, figurative system and structure have their own characteristics. In order to bring these processes to the world level and achieve the perfection of translated works, deep scientific research is needed - the imperative of the times. In the translation of Zulfiya's works, not only the realities of the Soviet era, but also the realities of the ancient past of the Uzbek people, as well as the socio-political realities of the time of independence, are quite often encountered. When they are translated into English, they should be left in the same version as in Uzbek.

⁸³ Zulfiya. I was in love. Poetry. Translation by B. Kholbekova . Tashkent. "Academic Edition" p. 33

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